

A Nonparametric F-Distribution Anomaly Detector for Hyperspectral Imagery

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Abstract—An innovative idea is proposed and its application to hyperspectral imagery is presented, as a viable alternative to testing sample hypothesis using conventional methods. This idea led to the design of two novel algorithms for anomaly detection. The first existing algorithm, referred to as *semiparametric* (*SemiP*), is based on some of the advances made on semiparametric inference. The second algorithm, proposed in this paper and referred to as a *combined F test* (CFT), is based on a nonparametric model and has its test statistic behaving asymptotically under the Fisher’s *F* family of distributions. A major drawback of the *SemiP* detector is its dependence on a function maximization routine, which requires initialization and no guarantees of convergence. The CFT detector is free of such dependence. Experimental results using real hyperspectral data are presented to illustrate the effectiveness of both algorithms in comparison to the industry standard approach. The CFT and *SemiP* detectors significantly outperformed the standard approach.

contain both spatial and spectral information about the objects and backgrounds in the scene. HS imagery has been used in various fields including geology, urban planning, geography, cartography, and the military. References to some of these topics in the context of remote sensing include [1]-[3].

The most robust class of algorithms for the aforementioned task using HS data is arguably the one that searches the pixels of sensor imagery for *rare* pixels whose information significantly differs from the local background (anomaly detection). The main advantage of using anomaly detectors is threefold: they may find both known and unknown target types; they do not require training, as neural networks do; and they are usually simple algorithms to implement. The main disadvantage of using anomaly detectors is that they often produce an intolerable high number of detections per scene, which—according to image analysts—becomes a nuisance rather than an aiding tool. A host of different types of anomaly detectors and their performances are described in [4]-[8].

My recent focus has been on a general idea for anomaly detection, one that performs a comparison between observations by an indirect means. The implementation of this idea has shown to preserve the number of *meaningful* anomaly detections and to significantly reduce the number of *meaningless* anomaly detections. (See [9] for comparison of a semiparametric approach to the industry standard technique and [10] for comparison of the same approach to three other techniques.) Fig. 1 clarifies the general principle.

Assume for the moment that a sampling mechanism is applied locally to hyperspectral imagery, where two samples are drawn and compared between the two. Three particular study cases are often found in this type of comparison: (1) results from two relatively pure samples belonging to the same population (*Y* in Fig. 1), (2) results from two relatively pure samples belonging to distinct populations (*X* and *Y*), and (3) results from a composite

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral sensors (HS) have become quite popular for applications requiring detection and classification of different materials. Their popularity over broadband sensors (e.g., forward looking infrared) is due to the fact that these passive sensors simultaneously record images for hundreds of contiguous and narrowly spaced regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. Each image corresponds to the same ground scene, thus creating a cube of images that

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Figure 1 - The number of *nuisance* detections may be significantly reduced by comparing, instead, the union of candidate samples to one of the candidates. Another advantage of using this principle is that the number of *meaningful* detections is preserved.

sample (XY mixture) and a single component (e.g., Y) sample of that mixture. For example, a comparison between two observations sampled from the same tree class falls under case 1, a comparison between a sample from a motor vehicle and a sample from a surrounding grassy area falls under case 2, and a comparison between a sample with two components (e.g., a tree and its shadow) and a sample from one of these components (e.g., shadow) falls under case 3.

Using a typical inside/outside window mechanism (see, Section 4) to sample the image for local anomaly detection, results have been shown [9]-[10] that case 3 appears quite often and is responsible for generating a high number of nuisance detections. The reason is that region discontinuities are abundant in scene imagery. Local anomaly detectors based on conventional statistical methods tend to declare a sample of a shadow, for instance, as being anomalous to a sample consisting of both tree and shadow components. This declaration is correct in the statistical sense but also unfortunate.

Rosario [9] converted this *weakness* to strength by proposing to compare in some form the union of the two samples to one of the individual observations. Fig. 1 depicts the notion of this indirect approach and its relevance to comparing two samples. Using the proposed notion, it is plausible that results for cases 1 and 2 would be unaffected in the statistical sense, but that results for case 3 would be affected, as shown, because the construction of a new sample (consisting of both XY and Y) merely adds more evidence about Y , making the original composite sample XY a *softer* anomaly in respect to the combined sample XY . This notion was implemented in the context of local anomaly detection via a semiparametric (logistic) model quite successfully, see [9]-[10]. The pragmatic aspect of the model's solution, however, was less than desirable because

it required the utility of an unconstrained maximization routine, whose convergence may depend on parameter initialization.

The focus in this paper is to propose a new anomaly detector using the same principle of indirect comparison, but which does not require the utility of a maximization routine. This new detector is based on a nonparametric model and has an asymptotic behavior of Fisher's F distribution. The F distribution arises frequently as the null distribution of the test statistic, especially in likelihood-ratio tests, perhaps most notably in the analysis of variance (ANOVA), see, for instance, [11]. For convenience, this detector will be referred to as the *Combined F-test* (CFT) detector to emphasize the combined feature of the notion. Comparison results using HS imagery (HSI) will be presented for the three detectors: semiparametric, CFT, and Reed-Xiaoli (RX; the industry standard technique) [4].

2. SEMIPARAMETRIC APPROACH

This section describes a semiparametric (SemiP) anomaly detector [10] that elegantly tests a sample pair via the indirect comparison approach mentioned in Section 1.

Assume for the moment that two sets of mutually exclusive observations x_0 and x_1 of sizes n_0 and n_1 , respectively, are available for comparison from a general location in a hyperspectral cube. Observations here may be interpreted as a sequence of transformed radiance. Consider now a model, where these two sequences are statistically independent random variables consisting of independent and identically distributed (iid) components, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= [x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n_1}] \sim g_1(x) \\ x_0 &= [x_{01}, \dots, x_{0n_0}] \sim g_0(x), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where their distributions g_0 and g_1 are unknown, but modeled as follows:

$$g_1(x) = e^{\alpha + \beta x} g_0(x). \quad (2)$$

Notice that since g_1 is a density, $\beta = 0$ must imply that $\alpha = 0$, as α merely functions as a normalizing parameter. Notice also that if $\beta = 0$ then x_0 and x_1 belong to the same population (i.e., $g_1 = g_0$). Taking these comments in consideration, an anomaly detector can be designed from the following composite hypothesis test:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : \beta = 0 \quad (g_1 = g_0) \quad \text{anomaly absent} \\ H_1 : \beta \neq 0 \quad (g_1 \neq g_0) \quad \text{anomaly present} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Notice that since our focus is in rejecting the null hypothesis H_0 , it does not really matter whether (2) is valid or not. Local regions in the entire imagery may be individually tested yielding a binary surface that depicts hypothesis H_1 as “1” and H_0 as “0.” An isolated object is expected to produce a cluster of “1” values (anomalies) in this surface.

The detector is based on the asymptotic behavior of the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of β , $\hat{\beta}$, which can be shown [12] to be asymptotically Normal, or

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\beta} - \beta_0) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} N\left(0, \frac{\rho^{-1}(1 + \rho)^2}{Var(t)}\right) \quad (4)$$

where the combined sequence

$$t = (x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n_1}, x_{01}, \dots, x_{0n_0}) = (t_1, \dots, t_n),$$

$Var(t)$ is the variance of t , β_0 is the true value of β , $\rho = n_1/n_0$, $n = n_1 + n_0$, and \rightarrow means *converges to*.

Normalizing the left side of (4) by the MLE of $Var(t)$, $\hat{v}(t)$, then setting $\beta_0 = 0$, and squaring the final result, one can test H_0 in (3) with the following expression [9]:

$$\chi = n\rho(1 + \rho)^{-2} \hat{\beta}^2 \hat{V}(t) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \chi_1^2, \quad (5)$$

which has the chi-square distribution asymptotic behavior with one degree of freedom, χ_1^2 . A decision is based on the value of χ in (5), i.e., high values reject hypothesis H_0 , declaring anomalies. A threshold can be selected based on

the type I error probability (probability of rejecting H_0 , given that H_0 is true), which is under the user’s control.

The SemiP anomaly detector, as shown in (5), is based on a solid theory, but its implementation has some undesirable requirements. The most prominent one is a requirement to maximize the log likelihood function

$$\log[\zeta(\alpha, \beta, g_0)] = \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} (\alpha + \beta x_{1j}) - \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \log[1 + \rho \exp(\alpha + \beta t)], \quad (6)$$

which is a direct result from the likelihood function

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(\alpha, \beta, g_0) &= \prod_{i=1}^{n_0} g_0(x_{0i}) \prod_{j=1}^{n_1} \exp(\alpha + \beta x_{1j}) g_0(x_{1j}) \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^{n_0+n_1} g_0(t_i) \prod_{j=1}^{n_1} \exp(\alpha + \beta x_{1j}), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

in order to find the MLEs $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$. Both MLEs are required to find $\hat{V}(t)$ in (5), where it can be shown [9] that

$$\hat{V}(t) = \hat{E}(t^2) - \hat{E}^2(t), \quad (8)$$

where

$$\hat{E}(t^k) = \sum_i t_i^k \hat{g}_0(t_i) \quad (9)$$

and

$$\hat{g}_0(t_i) = \frac{1}{n_0} \frac{1}{1 + \rho \exp(\hat{\alpha} + \hat{\beta} t_i)}. \quad (10)$$

To maximize (6), one needs to employ a specialized subroutine that performs an unconstrained maximization. Unfortunately, this type of subroutines requires parameter initialization to converge to a solution. This dependence is potentially a serious drawback, which was not observed using imagery from the visible to short-wave infrared (V-SWIR) region of the electromagnetic spectrum, but was observed using imagery from the long-wave infrared (LWIR) region. (Results from the LWIR imagery could not be released in this paper because of restrictions imposed by the U.S. military.)

The drawback mentioned above can be circumvented by implementing the principle of indirect comparison via a different method—a combined F-distribution test, which is the proposed new method in this paper.

3. NONPARAMETRIC F TEST

CFT Assumptions and Hypothesis

In order to avoid using specialized subroutines and still benefit from the general principle of *combine/compare*, I

propose the following: Let random variables x_{ij} be observed according to the model

$$\begin{aligned} x_{1j} &= \theta_1 + \varepsilon_{1j}, & j &= 1, \dots, n_1 \\ x_{2k} &= \theta_2 + \varepsilon_{2k}, & k &= 1, \dots, n_2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

i. $E\varepsilon_{ij} = 0, \text{Var} \varepsilon_{ij} = \sigma_i^2 < \infty$, for $i = 1, 2$ and all j .

$\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_{ij}, \varepsilon_{i'j'}) = 0$ for all $i, i', j, \text{ and } j'$

unless $i = i'$ and $j = j'$.

ii. The ε_{ij} are independent under an unknown distribution.

(Details on the implementation of this model using HS data will be discussed in Section 4.)

Let the combined sample be represented by

$$y = (y_1, \dots, y_n) = (x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n_1}, x_{21}, \dots, x_{2n_2}), \quad (12)$$

where, $n = n_1 + n_2$, and let the expected value and variance of its components be $Ey_i = \theta$ and $\text{Var} y_i = \sigma^2 < \infty$, respectively. Now define

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_1 &\equiv \theta_2 - \theta_1 \\ \beta_2 &\equiv \theta - \theta_2 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

and consider the hypothesis

$$H : \begin{cases} \beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0 \\ \sigma_1^2 = \sigma_2^2 \end{cases}. \quad (14)$$

Without the Normality assumption in (11), deriving a test for hypothesis H can be quite difficult, hence, we shall rely on the *central limit theorem* (CLT) to design the new detector. (My previous experience with HS data has convinced me that a sample size greater than 40 satisfies the CLT large sample requirement for this data type.)

CFT Detector

Using the *weak law of large numbers* (WLLN) [13], the set of parameters $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta, \sigma_1^2, \sigma_2^2)$ can be estimated by the following *consistent* estimators: $(\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \bar{y}, s_1^2, s_2^2)$, respectively, where

$$\bar{x}_i = n_i^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} x_{ik}, \bar{y} = n^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^n y_k, s_i^2 = (n_i - 1)^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} (x_{ik} - \bar{x}_i)^2; i = 0, 1. \quad (15)$$

Following (15),

$$\hat{\beta}_1 = \bar{x}_2 - \bar{x}_1 \quad (16)$$

and

$$\hat{\beta}_2 = \bar{y} - \bar{x}_2 \quad (17)$$

also constitute a set of consistent estimators for β_1 and β_2 , respectively. Recall that statistical consistency implies that the estimator's mean is asymptotically unbiased (i.e., it converges to an intended value) and that its variance converges to *zero*, as the number of samples increases. Recall also that statistical independence implies that the joint distribution of independent random variables is equivalent to the multiplication of their individual distributions.

Using the independence assumptions in (11) and the results in (15), the expected values and variances of $\hat{\beta}_1$ and $\hat{\beta}_2$ are readily attained by

$$E(\hat{\beta}_1) = \theta_2 - \theta_1, \text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_1) = \frac{1}{n_2} \sigma_2^2 + \frac{1}{n_1} \sigma_1^2; \quad (18)$$

and

$$E(\hat{\beta}_2) = \theta - \theta_2, \text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_2) = \frac{1}{n} \sigma^2 + \frac{1}{n_2} \sigma_2^2. \quad (19)$$

Using the independence assumptions and (18)-(19), if the hypothesis H in (14) is true (let $\tau^2 = \sigma_1^2 = \sigma_2^2$), under general regularity conditions, CLT ensures that the random variables z_1 and z_2 (see below) converges in law to the standard Normal distribution $[N(0,1)]$, or

$$z_1 = \frac{\hat{\beta}_1 - \beta_1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} \sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{n_2} \sigma_2^2}} = \frac{\hat{\beta}_1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \tau}} \xrightarrow[n_2 \rightarrow \infty]{n_1 \rightarrow \infty} N(0,1), \quad (20)$$

and equivalently

$$z_2 = \frac{\hat{\beta}_2 - \beta_2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n_1} \sigma_1^2 + \frac{1}{n_2} \sigma_2^2}} = \frac{\hat{\beta}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{n_2} \tau}} \xrightarrow[n_2 \rightarrow \infty]{n \rightarrow \infty} N(0,1), \quad (21)$$

where, $\sigma^2 = \tau^2$ must also be true, under H . Using properties of the family of chi square distributions (see, for instance, [14]), the following are also true:

$$z_1^2 = \frac{\hat{\beta}_1^2}{\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right) \tau^2} \xrightarrow[n_2 \rightarrow \infty]{n_1 \rightarrow \infty} \chi_1^2 \quad (22)$$

and

$$z_2^2 = \frac{\hat{\beta}_2^2}{\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)\tau^2} \xrightarrow[n_2 \rightarrow \infty]{n \rightarrow \infty} \chi_1^2, \quad (23)$$

where χ_1^2 is the chi-square probability density function (pdf) with 1 degree of freedom (dof).

Under H_1 , I propose two estimators of τ^2 . One to be used in (22) and the other in (23), they are

$$S_1^2 = \frac{(n_2 - 1)s_2^2 + (n_1 - 1)s_1^2}{(n_2 - 1) + (n_1 - 1)} \quad (24)$$

and

$$S_2^2 = \frac{(n - 1)s^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{(n - 1) + (n_2 - 1)}, \quad (25)$$

respectively, where, $s_i^2 (i=1,2)$ are defined in (15), $s^2 = (n - 1)^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^n (y_k - \bar{y})^2$, $\bar{y} = n^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^n y_k$, and $n = n_1 + n_2$. Both estimators S_1^2 and S_2^2 are consistent. Consistency of S_1^2 and S_2^2 implies in this case that using the *Slutsky theorem* [15], the following converges in law to a F distribution of (1,1) dof:

$$Z_{CFT} = \rho \frac{\hat{\beta}_1^2 S_2^2}{\hat{\beta}_2^2 S_1^2} \xrightarrow[n_2 \rightarrow \infty]{n \rightarrow \infty} F_{1,1}, \quad (26)$$

where, $\rho = (n^{-1} + n_2^{-1})(n_1^{-1} + n_2^{-1})^{-1}$.

Testing hypothesis H in (14) using (26) constitutes the CFT detector. A decision threshold T is determined via $\int_T^\infty F_{1,1}(w) dw = \alpha$, where α is the *type I error* (i.e., the probability of rejecting H , given that H is true). The user chooses α , and for values of $Z_{CFT} > T$, hypothesis H is rejected implying that x_1 and x_2 are most likely sampled from different distributions; hence, they are anomalous to each other. Otherwise, they are likely sampled from the same distribution. Note that the comparison between x_1 and x_2 via (26) is done indirectly using (β_1, S_1^2) , which holds information of both samples individually, and (β_2, S_2^2) , which holds information of the combined sample y in (12).

4. COMPARATIVE RESULTS

This section applies the algorithms discussed thus far to forest radiance data and compare them to the industry standard technique: the RX anomaly detector [4].

Sampling Mechanism (Inside/Outside Windows)

The three techniques were implemented using the conventional inside-outside window approach, choosing *optimum* window sizes to account for the target-size range of interest (see the forest scene in Fig. 2). Two local windows were defined by their sizes: a 5x5 window and a 9x9 window. By collocating these windows concentrically in a particular location in the image, and denoting W_{in} as the inside window (the entire 5x5 gate), and W_{out} as the outside window (only the outmost pixels of the 9x9 gate), W_{in} was labeled as the test gate, and W_{out} as the reference gate. The reason for using only the outmost pixels of the 9x9 gate for the reference is to provide a guard region between W_{in} and W_{out} , so that the possibility of sampling parts of potential targets using W_{out} and comparing to the same target using W_{in} can be avoided.

The RX algorithm was implemented for a multivariate anomaly detection problem, where the spectral samples (vectors) using W_{in} and W_{out} were used as inputs for computing (27), as recommended by [4].

Both SemiP and CFT algorithms were implemented for an univariate anomaly detection problem, where a high-pass filter was applied in the spectral domain to the samples from W_{in} and W_{out} , in order to promote statistical independence; the angle between each filtered sample from W_{out} and its corresponding filtered sample mean was used to form x_0 in (1) and x_{1j} in (11), with the number of pixels in W_{out} equating to n_0 in (1) and to n_1 in (11); and the angle between each filtered sample from W_{out} and the corresponding filtered sample mean from W_{in} was used to form x_l in (1) and x_{2j} in (11), with the number of pixels in W_{out} also equating to n_1 in (1) and to n_2 in (11).

The window cells were systematically moved throughout the imagery and, at each pixel location, the following question was considered: Does the information from W_{out} and W_{in} belong to the same population, or class? If the answer is *no*, the test sample was labeled as an anomaly with respect to its surroundings at that location.

RX Algorithm

The RX anomaly detector is based on the generalized likelihood ratio test and on the assumption that the population distribution family of both test and reference samples are multivariate normal. A version of the RX anomaly detector can be represented by the following equation:

$$Z_{RX} = n(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{in} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{out})^t \mathbf{C}_{out}^{-1} (\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{in} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{out}) \quad (27)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{in}$ is a sample mean vector from a set of spectral vectors using W_{in} , the number of components in each spectral vector is equal to the number of bands; $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_{out}$ is similar but sampled from W_{out} ; \mathbf{C}_{out}^{-1} is the estimated inverse

variance-covariance matrix using all the n spectral vectors in W_{out} . (Note that standard techniques such as *pseudo-inversion* may be used to estimate C_{out}^{-1} in order to circumvent cases of singularity.)

HYDICE Dataset

An experiment was carried out on data set from the hyperspectral digital imagery collection experiment (HYDICE) sensor. The HYDICE sensor records 210 spectral bands in the visible-to-near infrared (VNIR) and short-wave infrared (SWIR), 0.4-2.5 μm , forming a cube of spatially registered pixels. Each pixel then in the scene represents a vector with 210 components.

To challenge the local anomaly detectors, I extracted a sub-cube sufficiently large from the HYDICE dataset that include various levels of local complexity. The sub-cube depicts the radiance from a particular type of terrain, forest and open grass. The imagery used are the so-called Forest Radiance I (FR-I) and its spectral averages—from 150 bands—are shown in Fig. 2 (far left), as two dimensional (2-*dim*) images. (Water absorption and low signal-to-noise ration bands were discarded, hence, only remaining 150 bands were used; the discarded bands are: 23rd-101st, 109th-136th, and 152nd-194th.) In FR-I, 14 stationary military vehicles can be observed on sparse grasses, near a forest in Aberdeen, MD. The military vehicles in FR-I are considered in this paper as the targets, they are approximately of the same size, with a few exceptions.

The goal of local anomaly detectors on these types of scenes is to hopefully be able to detect all the objects that seem clearly anomalous to its immediate surroundings and to minimize meaningless detection.

Results

ROC curves will be used in this subsection as a means to quantitatively compare the different approaches, but before I discuss the ROC curves, let me first make a few comments on the 2-*dim* output surfaces of the three detectors running on FR-I, Fig. 2 shows those surfaces. Notice in Fig. 2 that all three detectors perform as expected: they accentuate local anomalies in the scene, including of course the 14 targets near the treeline. The RX output surface was displayed without clipping the most dominant peaks. The *SemiP* and CFT surfaces, however, were clipped at values commensurate to the performance of the weakest target at each surface, so that the most dominant target responses would not overshadow the fact that even those weaker target responses are significantly stronger than clutter responses.

From Fig. 2, it is clear that the detector based on a conventional approach (RX) does a poor job suppressing the responses at locations in the scene that would not be

considered by a human analyst as important. Moving on to the ROC curves, consider Fig. 3.

Figure 3 shows ROC curves produced by the output of the three algorithms on the HYDICE data scenes shown in Fig. 2. Detection performance was measured using the ground truth information for the HYDICE imagery. I used the coordinates of all the rectangular target regions and their shadows to represent the ground truth target set; call it *TargetTruth*. If we denote the region outside the *TargetTruth* as *ClutterTruth*, then the intersection between *TargetTruth* and *ClutterTruth* is zero and the entire scene is the union of *TargetTruth* and *ClutterTruth*. In this paper, for a given decision threshold, the probability of target detection (PD) is measured as the proportion between the number of detected pixels belonging to *TargetTruth* over all pixels belonging to *TargetTruth*. On the other hand, the proportion of false alarms (PFA) is measured as the

Figure 2 - Decision surfaces for the HYDICE FR-I data, forest radiance. The intensity of local peaks reflects the strength of anomaly evidences as seen by different detectors.

Figure 3 - ROC curves for the HYDICE FR-I data, forest radiance. Proportion of false alarms (PFA) ranges from 0.0 to 0.9; probability of detection (PD) ranges from 0.0 to 1.0.

Figure 4 - ROC curves for the HYDICE FR-I data. PFA = 0.0 to 0.02; PD = 0.0 to 1.0.

proportion between the detected pixels belonging to *ClutterTruth* over all pixels belonging to *ClutterTruth*.

As it can be readily assessed from Fig. 3, the *SemiP* and CFT detectors clearly outperform the industry standard techniques in V-SWIR forest data. The differences in performance are better appreciated in Fig. 4, where PFA is further restricted to a maximum value of 0.02—extreme low number of false alarms.

5. CONCLUSION

I have presented an asymptotic-F-distribution based anomaly detector for HSI. The proposed method exploits the principle of combining samples to test a two-sample hypothesis. I showed performance agreement between the new detector (CFT) and an existing detector (*SemiP*) that also exploits the same principle. A major drawback of using

the *SemiP* detector is its dependence on a function maximization routine, which requires initialization and no guarantees of convergence. The CFT detector, on the other hand, does not have such dependence. Comparative performances were also shown for the industry standard technique (RX). The techniques based on the combining principle outperformed the conventional one.

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BIOGRAPHY

Dalton Rosario is a senior staff member in the EO-IR Image Processing Branch, Army Research Laboratory (ARL). He received a B.S.E.E. degree from the California State University, Fresno, in 1990, a M.S.E.E. degree from the Johns Hopkins University in 1995, and currently holds a Ph.D. candidacy in the University of Maryland at College Park. Since 1990, Dalton has been a member of the technical staff at ARL, where he has studied the detection, discrimination, and classification of broadband radar, infrared, and hyperspectral targets.

